

Tailoring of unsaturated polyesters for inhibition of double-base and composite modified double-base rocket propellants[†]

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Unsaturated polyesters have proved their potential for inhibition of double-base (DB) and composite modified double-base (CMDB) rocket propellants but usually suffer from slightly higher nitroglycerine (NG) absorption and lower flame retardant characteristics. This requires tailoring of their properties through different techniques. This review summarizes different techniques for this purpose and presents the data generated. The present status of these tailored/modified systems is also discussed in detail followed by future scope of research in this field.

Introduction

The main function of a propellant is to impart motion to a projectile. For space exploration and military applications, both solid and liquid propellants are used. However, from the point of view of safety, reliability, simplicity and long storage life, solid rocket propellants are preferred over liquid propellants^{1,2}. Solid propellants are classified as DB, composite, CMDB and fuel rich propellants. Depending upon the requirements, rocket propellant technologists choose the propellant and considering overall functional requirements of a rocket/missile, they desire the propellant to burn in a definite pattern. This definite pattern of burning is achieved by applying polymeric materials, which do not readily burn, over the propellant surface. These polymeric materials are called 'Inhibiting Materials' or 'Inhibitors' and the process of their application is known as 'Inhibition'. The performance of a rocket/missile depends not only on propellant, but to a large extent, on inhibition system also.

Essential requirements of inhibitors

Inert polymeric materials suitable for inhibition of rocket propellants must fulfill a number of requirements³ and important ones are given below :

- (i) Chemical compatibility with rocket propellants, i.e. not promoting its deterioration.
- (ii) Ability to form and maintain strong bond with propellant. Should resist delamination, cracking or interface separation due to self-stressing. Ability to bond itself onto the propellant on direct application by 'Casting Technique' without any barrier coat is considered an added attribute.

- (iii) Should have a low density, low volatile content, effective ablative and thermal insulating characteristics.
- (iv) Inhibitor's mechanical and physical properties should closely match with those of propellant in order to minimize differential expansion.
- (v) Absorption of nitroglycerine (NG), stabilizer and plasticizer from propellant to inhibitor should be as less as possible, so that the physical properties and ballistic performance during its storage are not adversely affected to the extent of vitiating their serviceability.
- (vi) Should not exhibit 'corrosivity' characteristics when placed in intimate contact with steel and aluminium alloys motors.
- (vii) Ability to produce a sufficient degree of translucent finish is desirable, in to order to facilitate visual inspection after inhibition.
- (viii) The inhibited propellants after conditioning at ambient, cold (~-40°) and hot (+50°) temperatures⁴ should give, successful performance during static evaluation. This is the most important test and even if a polymer meets all the requirements but fails in this test, it can not be used for inhibition of rocket propellants.

Various unsaturated polyesters for inhibition of DB and CMDB rocket propellants

The term 'Polyester' describes a class of materials formed as a result of condensation reaction of a polyhydric alcohol and polybasic acid. This includes both saturated as well as

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

unsaturated polyesters. The unsaturated polyester is produced when one of the reactants contain non-aromatic unsaturation and then, it is crosslinked with an unsaturated polymerizable monomer. By common usage, however, the term polyester when used alone is synonymous with unsaturated polyester^{5,6}. A large number of glycols, dibasic acids, unsaturated acids and crosslinking monomers are reported in the literature and depending on the desired properties in an unsaturated polyester, a formulation based on glycol, dibasic acid and unsaturated acid (mostly maleic acid/anhydride) is formulated and synthesis is done either by '1-step' or '2-step' polyesterification process followed by blending with a crosslinking monomer^{7,8}.

Major ingredients of DB and CMDDB propellants are nitrocellulose (NC) and nitroglycerine (NG) in addition to other minor ingredients such as stabilizer, non-explosive plasticizer, coolant, lubricant, opacifier and burning-rate modifier. As the major ingredients NC and NG are esters, it is considered logical to use polyesters, which have strong bond with DB and CMDDB propellants, for inhibition of DB and CMDDB propellants⁴.

Agarwal *et al.*⁹⁻¹² have formulated and synthesized a wide range of unsaturated polyesters – rigid, semi-rigid, flexible, semi-flexible and very flexible and characterized them for gel time (G_t), exotherm peak temperature (E_{pT}), tensile strength (TS), % elongation (E), bond strength (BS) with propellants, NG absorption/migration, heat resistance and flame retardance etc. The data generated on such polyesters indicate that the elongation depends upon chainlength of glycol or dibasic acid and if high E is required, a glycol or dibasic acid of high chainlength is used. As % E and TS are interrelated, polyesters with high % E have low TS. For high TS, glycol like propylene glycol (PG) alone or in combination with diethylene glycol (DEG) is invariably used. It is authors' observation that if TS is high, BS of polyesters with propellants is also high. At the same time, it is also proved that if TS (indicative of extent of crosslink density) is high, NG absorption is low. If TS decreases, NG absorption increases in a given series of unsaturated polyesters. The gel time (G_t) and exotherm peak temperature (E_{pT}) data for unsaturated polyesters are equally important and a compromise between them is worked out in such a way that the auto-ignition temperature of the propellant is not reached during gelling and at the same time, G_t is not unduly more. The gel time of an unsaturated polyester suitable as a barrier coat is 8–10 min whereas it is \approx 30–40 min for the main inhibitor.

At HEMRL (formerly known as ERDL), researchers have been working in the field of inhibition of rocket propellants for several years and a brief summary of potential inhibition

systems is as follows : (i) rigid polyester (PR-3) and semi-rigid polyester-2 (SRUP-2) – suitable as barrier coats, (ii) semi-flexible unsaturated polyester resin-4 (SFUPR-4) suitable as inhibitor without any barrier coat, for immediate ballistic evaluation, (iii) flexible unsaturated polyester-9 (FUP-9) – suitable for inhibition without any barrier coat, and (iv) very flexible unsaturated polyester or elastopolyester (EP-4) – suitable as a main inhibitor in conjunction with barrier coats.

The DB propellants inhibited with EP-4 using Acrolite-471 (a rigid and fast curing unsaturated polyester) have also undergone life assessment trails and a life of ten years has been assigned to these inhibited propellants. A limited life assessment study on FUP-9 suggests that it is a potential inhibitor for DB propellants without any barrier coat.

Tailoring of properties of unsaturated polyesters

A study of essential requirements for a polymeric material to be suitable as an inhibitor for rocket propellants suggests that it should possess good tensile strength, high elongation, high bond strength with propellants, low NG/plasticizer absorption/migration and high flame retardance. Unsaturated polyesters have proved their potential for inhibition of DB/CMDDB rocket propellants but usually suffer from 2 minor drawbacks – slightly higher NG absorption/migration and low flame retardance. The tailoring of properties of unsaturated polyesters in order to make them more suitable/better for inhibition of DB/CMDDB rocket propellants is usually done through (i) formulation, (ii) methods of polyesterification, (iii) use of different crosslinking monomers and (iv) addition of fillers.

Formulation :

In the light of requirements and properties imparted by various glycols/acids, selection of a glycol/acid is done. The effect of variation of glycol in the formulation on some properties of polyesters is given in Tables 1 and 2.

Gel time (G_t) and exotherm peak temperature (E_{pT}) : The data on gel time and exotherm peak temperature for PR-3, FUP-0 and FUP-10 is given in Table 1. It is seen that as the chainlength of the glycol increases, gel time gradually increases but exotherm peak temperature decreases. PR-3, based on a short chain glycol (PG), shows highest peak exotherm and FUP-10, based on a longchain glycol (PEG-200) possesses lowest peak exotherm, whereas FUP-0 based on a medium chain length glycol, i.e. DEG possesses exotherm peak temperature which is in between. This may be explained on the basis of molecular weight per unsaturated acid¹³. As the shortchain glycol (PG) is replaced by a longchain glycol (PEG), molecular weight per unsaturated

Table 1. Effect of glycols on some properties of polyesters

Resin	Formulation*					G_t min	TS kg cm ⁻²	E %	BS with DB propellants kg cm ⁻²	NG absorption (after 14 days), %
	PG	DEG	PEG- 200	IPA	MAn					
PR-3	1.0	–	–	0.33	0.67	16.0	300	8	85	2.5
FUP-0	–	1.0	–	0.33	0.67	37.0	135	19	35	9.6
FUP-10	–	–	1.0	0.33	0.67	63.0	15	27	10	Very high

*Acid values at the end of first and second steps are 50 ± 2.

Table 2A. Effect of variation of chainlength of diabasic acid (DA) on some properties of polyesters

Resin	Formulation*				G_t min	E_{PT} °C	TS kg cm ⁻²	E %	BS with CMDB propellants kg cm ⁻²	NG absorption (after 10 days) %
	Molar composition, mole									
	MEXDIOL	IPA	DA	MAn						
NUP (III)-A	12.0	2.0	5.0 Succinic	5.0	51.0	64.1	118.0	8.3	7.6	4.0
NUP (III)-B	12.0	2.0	5.0 Adipic	5.0	62.0	60.0	21.0	35.0	6.0	4.5
NUP (III)-C	12.0	2.0	5.0 Suberic	5.0	71.0	58.2	11.0	49.0	4.5	5.0
NUP (III)-D	12.0	2.0	5.0 Sebacic	5.0	74.0	56.0	10.0	49.2	3.1	6.0

*Acid values at the end of first, second and third steps are 50 ± 2.

Table 2B. Effect of acids on some properties of unsaturated polyesters

Resin	Formulation*					G_t min	TS kg cm ⁻²	E %	BS with DB propellants kg cm ⁻²	NG absorption (after 18 days), %
	DEG	PAn	TCPAn	TBPAn	MAn					
NHP	1.0	0.5	–	–	0.5	5.5	46	25	29	7.09
CP	1.0	–	–	–	0.5	18.0	100	18	48	3.56
BP	1.0	–	0.5	0.5	0.5	55.0	136	5	51	2.97

*Acid values at the end of first and second steps are 50 ± 2.

acid increases and consequently, number of polyester chain decreases in order to maintain the same molecular weight (the number average molecular weight, \bar{M}_n , is of the same order in case of all these polyesters as the acid value is practically same). It means that the polyester chains based on PEG-200 are longer whereas based on PG are shorter. Because longer chain molecules are less reactive than the shortchain molecules, it is expected that FUP-10 will have a longer gel time than FUP-0 and PR-3 which is observed experimentally.

The bond energy¹⁴ of carbon-carbon double bond, i.e. –C=C– bond is 145.8 kcal mol⁻¹ and that of carbon-carbon single bond, i.e. –C–C– bond is 82.6 kcal mol⁻¹. The polyester chains are linked to one another through the

conversion of double bonds into single bonds during curing/crosslinking with the crosslinking monomer, i.e. styrene. As explained, the number of polyester chains decreases with the replacement of PG by DEG and PEG-200 and, therefore, amount of heat liberated during gelling decreases from PR-3 to FUP-10. In other words, exotherm peak temperature decreases from PR-3 to FUP-10.

Tensile strength and % elongation : Tensile strength and % elongation data for different polyesters is given in Table 1 and it is observed that both are closely related. In general, TS decreases with the increase in chainlength of glycol but the trend is reversed in the case of % E . This is a shared general characteristic of polyesters and most other crosslinked polymeric. This may also be explained using

the analogy of gel time and exotherm peak temperature. As shortchain glycol (PG) is replaced by longchain glycol, (PEG-200), the number of polyester chains decreases in order to achieve the same molecular weight. Because the polyester chains are linked to one another through the unsaturated linkages in the polyester chains and as the number of polyester chains decreases, crosslink density also decreases, with a corresponding decrease in TS and increase in % *E* from PR-3 to FUP-10.

Bond strength with propellants : The bond strength of these polyesters decreases as the shortchain glycol (PG) is replaced by longchain glycols, i.e. DEG and PEG-200. The reason for this is not well understood but can be explained with the help of one practical observation, i.e. rigid and fast-curing polyesters have strong bonds with DB/CMDB propellants while flexible and slow-curing polyesters have weak bonds.

Nitroglycerine (NG) absorption migration : The NG absorption increases from PR-3 to FUP-10 i.e. when short-chain glycol (PG) is replaced by long chain glycols i.e. DEG and PEG-200. This is because of the decreased tightness of molecular structures of the resulting polyesters as indicated by the tensile strength / % elongation data (Table 1) on replacement of shortchain glycol (PG) by longchain glycols, i.e. DEG and PEG-200. The decrease in the tightness of molecular structures from PR-3 to FUP-10 enhances seepage of NG molecules through these products leading to increase in NG absorption in this order.

The effect of variation of acids on some properties of polyesters is given in Tables 2A and 2B^{15,16}. The effect of chainlength of acids is similar to that of glycol chainlength and may be explained accordingly. Some properties of phthalic anhydride (PAN) based polyester are given in Table 2B along with the properties of chloropolyester (based on tetrachlorophthalic anhydride, TCPAN) and bromopolyester (based on tetrabromophthalic anhydride, TBPAN). A comparison of various properties suggests that gel time, TS, and bond strength with propellants follow the order : BP > CP > NHP, whereas the order for % *E* and NG absorption is just opposite, i.e. NHP > CP > BP. This may be explained

in terms of structural aspects derived with the help of IR and NMR by Agrawal *et al.*¹⁵.

Method of polyesterification :

Polyesterification between diol and dibasic acid is usually done by (i) 1-step process, (ii) 2-step process and (iii) 3-step process (patented by Agrawal *et al.* in 1998).

The general structure of an unsaturated polyester synthesized by 2-step polyesterification process may be shown as :

It is evident that the distance between the crosslinking sites along the polyester chain depends on chainlength of glycol/ acid and it increases/decreases accordingly. This distance is mainly responsible for the trend among various properties before and after curing. However, there is no instrumental technique by which the distance between the crosslinking sites may be experimentally determined.

The commercially available unsaturated polyesters are generally manufactured by 1-Step polyesterification process and as a result, possess poor flexibility and inferior heat resistance. At the same time, higher temperature of reaction in the 1-Step process converts maleic configuration to fumaric configuration. On the contrary, unsaturated polyesters, chloropolyesters and novel unsaturated polyesters for inhibition of DB and CMDB propellants are synthesized by 2-Step polyesterification process which imparts more regular structure, better flexibility and greater heat resistance to the resulting polyesters.

The effect of 'Methods of Polyesterification' on various properties is depicted in Table 3. It is seen from the data that the order of G_t is NUP (I) < NUP (II) < NUP (III), whereas the order for tensile strength is NUP (I) > NUP (II) > NUP (III). Further, % *E* gradually increases from NUP (I) to NUP (III). However, there is no specific trend for NG

Table 3. Effect of 'methods of polyesterification' on some DEG based NUPs

Resin	Formulation*				Method	Properties			
	DEG	IPA	AA	MAn		G_t min	TS kg cm ⁻²	<i>E</i> %	NG absorption (after 8 days) %
NUP (I)	12.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	1-Step	11.0	41.0	26.0	23.98
NUP (II)	12.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	2-Step	12.5	30.0	30.0	32.05
NUP (III)	12.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	3-Step	23.3	5.1	36.0	26.93

*Acid values at the end of all steps are 50 ± 2.

sulting cured polyesters may be varied by the choice of monomers employed. At the same time, varying quantities of monomer produce a series of polyesters that possess a wide range of properties. Styrene monomer is most widely used crosslinking monomer for unsaturated polyesters. MMA is used in place of styrene or as a partial replacement of styrene for specific applications such as inhibition of smokeless CMDB propellants for 'Fire and Forget Type' missiles where inhibitor should also be smokeless or should give reduced levels of smoke.

The effect of variation of styrene monomer on some properties of FUP-9 is shown in Table 4. It is seen from the data that viscosity decreases as the percentage of styrene monomer increases which is obvious and is due to the dilution effect of added styrene monomer. Further, TS increases with an increase in styrene monomer concentration with corresponding decrease in % elongation¹⁹. As expected, NG absorption decreases in line with TS data.

Table 4. Effect of variation of styrene monomer on some properties of FUP-9

FUP-9 : Styrene %	Viscosity cP	Gel time min	Tensile strength kg cm ⁻²	Elongation %	NG absorption %
70-30	110	-	60	19	12.96
60-40	60	15.1	148	13	10.00
50-50	36	11.7	185	10	9.30
40-60	27	-	210	10	8.38

The effect of partial replacement of styrene monomer by MMA is depicted in Table 5. The presence of MMA retards curing of polyesters, and as a result, G_t increases on partial replacement of styrene monomer by MMA. Further, FUP-9 with MMA alone as a crosslinking monomer does not cure at room temperature.

Table 5. Effect of partial replacement of styrene by MMA on properties of FUP-9 (FUP-9 : styrene : : 60 : 40) system

Replacement of styrene by MMA %	Gel time min	Viscosity cP	Tensile strength kg cm ⁻²	Elongation %	NG absorption (after 10 days), %
0	15.1	60	148	13	10.08
25	17.2	58	155	14	5.12
50	26.1	54	39	32	10.18
100	Does not cure at room temperature				

Addition of fillers :

A variety of techniques have been employed in an attempt to confer flame retardant characteristics to unsatur-

ated polyester resins²⁰. These are : (i) addition of inorganic fillers, (ii) addition of organic additives, (iii) combination of (i) and (ii), and (iv) introduction of a flame retardant element in the polyester backbone.

However, use of inorganic fillers such as antimony trioxide, alumina trihydrate and zinc borate or its complex etc. appear to be interesting in order to impart flame retardant characteristics as these are usually inexpensive and in many cases, help to improve mechanical properties²¹.

The effect of addition of filler (alumina trihydrate) on some properties of SFUP-4 is given in Table 6. The data indicate that TS increases with an increase in the percentage of filler but percent elongation, as expected, decreases²². The increase in TS is attributed to the reinforcement of resin matrix on addition of fillers. Also, addition of fillers results in decrease in NG absorption which is proportional to the quantity of resin and decreases with an increase in filler concentration. Similarly, burn-rate of resin decreases in this order or in other words, flame retardant characteristics of resin increases with the increase in the filler content²³⁻²⁶.

Table 6. Effect of variation of filler (alumina trihydrate) on some properties of SFUP-4

Resin	% Filler (alumina trihydrate)	G_t min	Tensile strength kg cm ⁻²	Elongation %	NG absorption (after 14 days) %	Burning rate mm s ⁻¹
SEUP-4	0	20.5	36.36	18.6	2.50	0.30
	10	9.5	60.54	10.5	1.52	0.29
	30	9.0	70.14	9.5	1.33	0.15
	50	7.5	70.07	6.7	1.13	(++)

(++) Non-burning.

The data on various properties of filled SFUP-4 indicates that G_t , TS, and flame retardance increase whereas NG migration decrease as filler content increases from 0-50%. Therefore, these properties may be tailored in the light of the above findings. This technique of minor modification in the properties of unsaturated polyesters is very promising and cost-effective.

Future scope

The inhibition of DB and CMDB rocket propellants has always been a difficult problem because of the presence of NG in these propellants and its subsequent migration from the propellants towards inhibitors and is still open for further work in search of an ideal inhibitor. The unsaturated polyesters are generally used for inhibition of DB and CMDB propellants mainly due to their strong bond with propellants

and cost. The vast data generated by Agrawal *et al.* suggest that an unsaturated polyester possessing following properties : (i) bond strength (without inter-positioning a barrier coat) with propellants, $\text{kg cm}^{-2} \approx 50.0$ (ii) tensile strength, $\text{kg cm}^{-2} \approx 80-100$, (iii) elongation, $\% \approx 40-50$, (iv) explosive plasticizer (NG)/non-explosive plasticizer absorption, $\% \approx 5-6$ will serve as an ideal inhibitor for them.

NUP (III) class of unsaturated polyesters with a unique combination of higher elongation and lower NG migration/absorption is likely to be a formidable candidate for inhibition of CMDDB propellants. The flame retardancy of NUP (III) may be increased by the introduction of elements like chlorine or bromine or boron or phosphorous in their structures or use of chloro/bromo styrene in combination with styrene monomer.

Conclusions

Based on voluminous data generated by us and also reported in the literature on tailoring of properties of unsaturated polyesters, it may be concluded,

1. If TS increases \longrightarrow
 - * BS with rocket propellants increases
 - * NG/Plasticizer migration decreases
 - * Heat resistance increases
2. If E increases, \longrightarrow
 - ** NG/Plasticier migration increases
 - ** BS with rocket propellant decreases
 - ** Heat resistance decreases
3. 'Formulation' and 'Method of Polyesterification', impart considerable changes in properties whereas variation of 'crosslinking monomers' and 'fillers' impart only minor changes.
4. Addition of fillers leads to increase in TS but decrease in elongation and NG migration/absorption. Addition of inorganic fillers also leads to increase in flame retardance.

Of course, the conclusions of this study are in context with unsaturated polyesters but are equally applicable to other polymeric materials as well.

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